

RESPONDENT

D7.2 – Plan for Dissemination and Communication

Submission date: 28th April 2023

Due date: 30th April 2023

DOCUMENT SUMMARY INFORMATION

Grant Agreement No	101082355	Acronym	RESPONDENT
Full Title	Renewable Energy Sources Power FOrcasting and SyNchronisation for Smart Grid NEtworks MaNagement		
Start Date	01/11/2022	Duration	30 months
Deliverable	D7.2: Plan for Dissemination and Communication		
Work Package	WP7 – Roadmap to Impact		
Type	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Beneficiary	CARR		
Authors	Benjamin Moore (CARR)		
Co-authors	Linda Henriksson (CARR)		
Reviewers	Effie Makri (FINT), Ane Miren Florez Tapia (VICOM)		

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101082355

The material presented and views expressed here are the responsibility of the author(s) only. The European Commission takes no responsibility for any use made of the information set out.

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	16/02/2023	Initial Deliverable Structure	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR)
V0.2	03/04/2023	75% of content inserted	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR)
V0.3	14/04/2023	90% of content inserted – edits required	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR)
V0.4	17/04/2023	Internal review of first draft	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR)
V0.5	24/04/2023	Incorporated partner feedback following review	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR) Effie Makri (FINT) Ane Miren Florez Tapia (VICOM)
V0.6	26/04/2023	Final review	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR)
V1.0	27/04/2023	Quality review check	Benjamin Moore (CARR) Linda Henriksson (CARR)

PROJECT PARTNERS

Partner	Country	Short name
FUTURE INTELLIGENCE EREVNA TILEPIKINONIAKON KE PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON EPE	Greece	FINT
FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	Spain	VICOM
CARR COMMUNICATIONS LIMITED	Ireland	CARR
KIEFER TEK ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHYNIS	Greece	KIEFER
GREENESCO ENERGEIAKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA	Greece	GREEN
ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA SA	Spain	EPESA
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	Spain	IREC-CERCA
ELECTROTECNICA DEL URUMEA SL	Spain	EUSKABEA

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
ERs	Exploitable Results
EO	Earth Observation
GA	Grant Agreement
HE	Horizon Europe
IoT	Internet of Things
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
T&S	Timing and Synchronisation
TSO	Transmission System Operator
WAMS	Wide Area Monitoring Systems
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the strategy for the communication and dissemination of RESPONDENT's objectives and results as a Horizon Europe project. The primary dissemination objective of RESPONDENT is to ensure that all results are made available to relevant stakeholders, and that the reasons for the results being of interest, benefit, and relevance to them are communicated effectively. This in turn facilitates exploitation and take-up of the results by relevant stakeholders.

RESPONDENT will result in a solution suite that will develop and promote the integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into Europe's existing power grids, as well as to demonstrate their viability and reliability compared to traditional sources of energy that are wreaking havoc on global temperatures and accelerating the most destructive impacts of our rapidly changing climate. These broad messages and objectives will form the basis of the communication and dissemination activities.

The RESPONDENT approach to dissemination is inclusive and iterative. The project partners are involved in the dissemination activities from the planning stage through to implementation over the 30-month lifespan of the project.

The strategy outlined in this document describes the RESPONDENT objectives and approach, and goes on to identify key audiences, messages, channels, and material for dissemination. It outlines relevant scientific and industry publications, conferences and other events to target, networking and knowledge transfer efforts, and media relations. It lists the dissemination KPIs and carves out a timeline for activities, as well as performance measurement and analysis. A section on the management of the dissemination activities is included as well.

The mapping of target audiences is a continuous exercise. Key target audience groups include RES aggregators, TSOs/DSOs, the research and scientific community, as well as society at large.

Digital and social channels have a central role to play in the strategy, as they provide extensive opportunities for RESPONDENT to inform, engage, and promote take-up of the project results, all the while building and strengthening relationships with the target audiences. The dissemination channels include but are not limited to the project website, social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube), newsletters, and traditional media outlets. All promotional material will be produced in line with the RESPONDENT Brand guidelines, as described in *D7.1 – RESPONDENT Website*.

Key performance indicators – numerical targets that facilitate the measuring of how well the project achieves its dissemination goals – have been set, and an indicative timeline for dissemination activities up to Month 15, when the first Dissemination and Communication report is due, has been developed to ensure strategic and effective actions. As the RESPONDENT pilot demonstrations will take place in Greece and Spain, the project partners based in the pilot areas will play a key role in the dissemination activities.

Our open access approach ensures that the results of our research contribute invaluable knowledge into the marketplace of climate change solutions. We provide online access to scientific information that is free of charge and reusable. To acknowledge the support received under the Horizon Europe programme, we include the EU emblem and the funding acknowledgement in all dissemination materials.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
Table of Contents	6
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	9
1.2 Intended readership	10
1.3 Relationship with other RESPONDENT deliverables.....	10
2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy	11
2.1 Objectives	11
2.2 Overview of Strategy	13
2.3 Development and Marketing of New Tools and Processes.....	14
2.4 Target Audiences	16
2.5 Key Messages	17
2.6 Digital Communication and Dissemination Channels	17
2.6.1 Website.....	18
2.6.2 LinkedIn	19
2.6.3 Twitter	20
2.6.4 YouTube.....	21
2.6.6 Newsletter	21
2.7 Promotional Material	21
2.8 Publications	22
2.9 Events	25
2.10 Clustering, networking, and knowledge transfer activities.....	27
2.10.1 Clustering with related projects	27
2.10.2 Building networks.....	27
2.10.3 Knowledge transfer activities	28
2.11 Media and multipliers	28
2.12 Timeline of Activities	29
2.13 Performance Measurement and Analysis	30
2.13.1 Key Performance Indicators	30
2.13.2 Online Analytics.....	31
2.14 Management and Administration of Dissemination Activities	32
2.14.1 Dissemination Reporting, Compliance, and Obligation to Disseminate Results.....	32

2.14.2 Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data	33
2.14.3 Acknowledgement of EU Funding	33
2.14.4 Risk Management	34
3 Conclusions	35
References	36
Annexes	37
A1: Website Privacy Policy	37
A2: Cookie Policy	43
A3: Related Projects	45

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: RESPONDENT Strategic Dissemination Approach	13
Figure 2: RESPONDENT Communication and Dissemination Plan.....	14
Figure 3: RESPONDENT's Key Exploitable Results.....	15
Figure 4: RESPONDENT Target Audiences.....	16
Figure 5: RESPONDENT Key Messages.....	17
Figure 6: RESPONDENT Website Landing Page.....	19
Figure 7: RESPONDENT LinkedIn Page.....	20
Figure 8: RESPONDENT Twitter Page.....	20
Figure 9: RESPONDENT YouTube Page.....	21
Figure 10: Dissemination and Communication Tracker.....	23

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Relationship between D7.2 and other RESPONDENT deliverables	10
Table 2: RESPONDENT Objectives	11
Table 3: Selection of Targeted Journals.....	23
Table 4: Selection of Targeted Events.....	24
Table 5: Indicative Timeline of Activities.....	29
Table 6: Key Performance Indicators.....	30

1 Introduction

The goal of an effective communication and dissemination strategy document should be to outline the approach and concrete actions that will be taken to ensure the successful promotion of the project and subsequent wide dissemination and understanding of its emerging results.

This deliverable establishes the comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy that will be adopted for RESPONDENT, based on the initial plans included in the project's Grant Agreement (GA), in accordance with the Horizon Europe (HE) guiding principles, and as agreed to among the consortium partners.

As with any practical plan for communication and dissemination, RESPONDENT's will be one that is inherently dynamic and adaptable, one that can be modified and built upon as the project progresses and its solutions are realised. It will be followed by deliverable *D7.3 – Dissemination and Communication Report 1* in Month 15 of the project, as well as deliverable *D7.4 - Dissemination and Communication Report 2* in Month 30.

Although CARR is the leader of WP7, it is important to note that the communication and dissemination activities can and must be shared by all project partners to ensure their successful implementation and maximise outreach. Such contributions may include attendance at conferences and other events, submissions to scientific journals and academic papers, as well as networking with key stakeholders and end-user beneficiaries at both national and EU levels.

RESPONDENT aims to contribute significantly to the increased uptake of renewable energy sources (RES), such as solar, wind, and hydropower, in the EU, a crucial goal if Europe is to achieve its aspiration to transform to a climate-neutral economy by the year 2050. The desire of the bloc to radically shift from fossil fuels to RES and decarbonise its energy sector has been given careful consideration and stressed by the consortium partners, with the communication and dissemination strategies designed from the outset to encourage such a lofty goal.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to serve as a blueprint and guidebook for ensuring optimal impact in terms of communication and dissemination of the project's activities, progress, and results. This will be achieved by establishing a clear strategy designed to project paramount visibility and inform target audiences of the project's solutions to tackle the looming threat of our climate crisis. This deliverable will therefore outline and describe RESPONDENT's strategy in this respect, designed in such a way as to deliver the project results to the appropriate stakeholders in both a suitable and easily accessible format.

As it is intended for all consortium partners to contribute to the communication and dissemination efforts of the project, it is important to consolidate all of the relevant details in to one single, informative document that can be easily referenced and understood by the reader. A parallel purpose of this document is to enable the project partners to familiarise themselves with the overall framework of the communication and dissemination strategy.

1.2 Intended readership

This deliverable is disseminated both to the consortium partners of RESPONDENT, as well as to any external stakeholders or interested parties outside of the project. As this deliverable is public, it is openly accessible to the public and/or any other person/people who may wish to view it.

Although this deliverable is public, it will be of particular interest to consortium members that are involved in communication and dissemination activities, now or in the future of the project. The adopted strategy will also be beneficial to all members by providing them with a guidebook that will assist to expound the broader communication and dissemination activities of the project, and to help partners understand the ways in which they can contribute and participate in actions that are intended to amplify RESPONDENT'S impact.

1.3 Relationship with other RESPONDENT deliverables

This deliverable is closely linked to the deliverables listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between D7.2 and other RESPONDENT deliverables

Deliverable	Name of Deliverable	Link to D7.2
D7.1	Project Website and Branding	D7.1 established the project's profile to external entities and serves as the nucleus for all dissemination activities. The branding outlined in D7.1 therefore guides the development of all communication and dissemination materials.
D7.3	Dissemination and Communication Report 1	D7.3 will monitor the execution of RESPONDENT's communication and dissemination strategy (D7.2)
D7.4	Dissemination and Communication Report 2	D7.4 will monitor the execution of RESPONDENT's communication and dissemination strategy (D7.2)

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

As this deliverable has been drafted in the early months of the project, the primary focus has been to present the initial strategy for communication and dissemination, as well as to outline how it will be implemented as the project progresses. The strategy was conceptualised from the inauguration of the project to disseminate its results and to raise awareness of the project more broadly.

This strategy will outline the objectives and methods of RESPONDENT in this regard, in addition to identifying the initial key audiences, messages, channels, and material for dissemination, among other considerations.

2.1 Objectives

While the work of RESPONDENT is of significance, it is recognised by the consortium partners that there exists several challenges that must be overcome to initiate a successful communication and dissemination strategy.

One such challenge to consider is the specified nature of the audiences that RESPONDENT plans to target and the most efficient ways of connecting with these stakeholders. Further challenges include conceptualising the outcomes of RESPONDENT that are tangible and immediately relevant to these stakeholders, and to acknowledge that the solutions developed by the project will initially be of most interest to those operating in specific fields. With these points in mind, it is crucial that communication and dissemination activities, in conjunction with key messages and channels, are adjusted for individual audiences and not presented as simply a catch-all method to have the broadest possible appeal.

Communication and dissemination activities will be guided by the project's objectives. In order for these efforts to be impactful, we must first look at the overall objectives of RESPONDENT, as outlined in the GA and presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: RESPONDENT Objectives

Objective	Description
A	<p>A.1 Achieve highly accurate, site-specific, short- to mid-term weather forecasting using well-established weather models, Copernicus EO data, in-situ RES site-specific measurements, and historical weather data, by exploiting power generation forecasting AI/ML algorithm processing.</p> <p>A.2 Achieve precise, short- to mid-term, and error free RES power generation forecasting by exploiting the AI-powered weather forecasting results and power conversion models for RES types (solar, wind and hydro-electric).</p>
B	Provide accurate short-to mid-term power demand forecasting, combining Copernicus EO weather data, historical and simulated data, and relevant socio-economic factors into the demand forecasting AI/ML, agent-based and multiphysics simulations.

C	<p>C.1 Integration of Galileo receiver chipset into commercially available PMUs utilising the Galileo Timing and Synchronisation service to augment the T&S and monitoring capabilities of the smart grid WAMS.</p> <p>C.2 Development of Galileo-enabled PMU signal monitoring module and dashboard, allowing the grid operator to efficiently monitor the grid state and its dynamic behaviour.</p>
D	Support the supply of secure, stable, and seamless power to the grid, by providing forecasting solutions for both power generation and demand and by enabling the integration of Variable RES and DERs through the precise synchronisation and monitoring of the power grid.

In order to effectively promote and disseminate the research and activities involved in these objectives, the primary dissemination objective of the RESPONDENT project is to ensure that all results are made available to relevant stakeholders, and that the reasons for the results being of interest, benefit, and relevance to them is competently communicated and explained. Such actions will, in turn, ensure that exploitation and adoption of the project's results are embraced by the end-users.

As part of a proficient communication and dissemination strategy, these ambitions can be realised in three distinct but interrelated ways:

- **Dissemination for awareness**
 - Resulting in relevant stakeholders being informed about the research, its progress, results, and project activities (distributing information through reports, publishing papers, conference presentations, newsletters, and other digital and traditional dissemination channels)
- **Dissemination for understanding**
 - Resulting in stakeholders acquiring a deeper understanding of the project aims and solutions (distributing information in a more interactive manner, e.g., workshops and two-way dissemination channels)
- **Dissemination for action**
 - Resulting in real change, in the breakthrough innovation being upscaled, replicated, or transformed and embedded in the new contexts; stakeholder engagement (directed, systematic, proactive engagement involving adaption and implementation).

The ultimate goal of the RESPONDENT project is to introduce innovative methods to increase the viability and use of RES throughout the EU's energy sector. The decisive communication and dissemination objective will therefore be to obtain the attention of key stakeholders, thus securing the lasting legacy of RESPONDENT beyond the project's lifespan.

Gender and non-discrimination practices have also been considered as part of the project. As stated in RESPONDENT's GA and to ensure gender balance with respect to the decision making and leadership, the Technical Manager (Dr. Ane Miren Florez Tapia), the Communication and Dissemination Lead (Ms Linda Henriksson), the Innovation Manager (Ms Marta Fonrodona), and the Project Coordinator (Ms Effie Makri) are

all women. An equal measure of gender balance and inclusivity will also be ensured across all dissemination activities and materials (e.g., text, images, videos).

2.2 Overview of Strategy

The RESPONDENT dissemination and communication strategy will ensure that the project outcomes (including concepts, scientific results, methodologies, etc.) are extensively circulated among the appropriate target audiences, at the appropriate times, and through the appropriate channels. Furthermore, the strategy will identify and encourage external stakeholders to contribute their insight to the development, evaluation, uptake, and exploitation of these outcomes.

As mentioned previously, RESPONDENT’s approach to dissemination is inclusive and iterative, and has been applied in the development of the strategy. At the outset of the planning phase for the strategy, the following eight steps were identified to achieve success:

1. Listening to and gathering insights
2. Setting specific dissemination objectives
3. Identifying relevant target audiences
4. Selecting the appropriate dissemination channels
5. Planning impactful activities
6. Defining and tailoring key messages accordingly
7. Implementing the dissemination activities
8. Evaluating and assessing the success of the activities

The RESPONDENT approach to a lucrative dissemination and communication strategy was developed with the following questions in mind: Why should we disseminate, what should we disseminate, to whom, and how?

Below, the RESPONDENT approach to dissemination has been summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: RESPONDENT Strategic Dissemination Approach

The RESPONDENT communication and dissemination strategy has been created with the intention of increasing the societal, environmental, innovation, and business impacts of the project in mind. Thus, the

dissemination efforts will naturally support and advance the exploitation and future success of the project’s results.

A grid of the RESPONENT plan for communication and dissemination is presented below in Figure 2.

Target audiences	RES Aggregators		TSO/DSOs		PMU Manufacturers		Research and Scientific Community		National and EU Energy/Grid Regulators		Society at Large
Communications channels	Project website	Social media (Twitter, LinkedIn)	Project newsletter	Broadcast media, national TV and radio	Print media	Research publications, such as research*eu, Horizon Magazine	Digital media (YouTube)	Academic conferences and research events	Peer-reviewed and open-access journals	Webinars, workshops, seminars	
Key messages	RESPONENT will... Help to increase the uptake of RES across Europe		Provide innovative, clean, affordable, and secure energy solution employing both Copernicus EO and Galileo services		Reduce Europe's dependency on fossil fuels	Increase energy security	Provide a complete power package of power forecasting and synchronisation for smart grids	Utilise weather-specific data to explicitly exploit the unique capabilities and offerings of the European EO programme		Contribute significantly to the European Green Deal	
Communication	1000 social media followers (LinkedIn and Twitter)	20 publications in industry magazines/articles in magazines	Mass media coverage (TV, radio)	8.000 visitors to the project website and 100 downloads	6 YouTube videos about the project	Monthly news updates and blog posts	6 press releases	2 technical and/or dissemination workshops	2 focus groups	Interview sessions at the end of each pilot	
Dissemination	2 open-access, peer reviewed scientific publications	2 conference presentations per year	1 trade fair during project duration	2 Workshops	1 White Paper	1 Public Webinar	Participation in dissemination services (e.g. Horizon Results Booster, Horizon Results Platform, Innovation radar)		3 events - 1 per pilot and 1 at the end of the project		

Figure 2: RESPONENT Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.3 Development and Marketing of New Tools and Processes

A key factor in the success of the project’s communication and dissemination plan will also be to prepare the RESPONENT solutions for the market, including the developed software and hardware tools and processes as shown in the figure below from the GA, as well as the exploration and development of partner and consortium-wide exploitation strategies.

KER:		Added Value	Type	Owner	Customer
1	RESPONDENT complete/holistic solution suite	Integrated, all-in-one highly efficient, low cost grid monitoring, stability & balancing	SW/ HW	Joint Venture (FINT, VICOM, IREC, EUS)	Smart Grid Operator, PPC, TSO/DSO (EPESA, Greek PPC, Greenesco)
2	AI/ML RES power generation forecasting module	High accuracy power accuracy, prediction reliability, low cost.	SW/ HW	Joint Venture (FINT, VICOM)	RES Aggregator (Kiefer, Greenesco)
3	AI/ML demand forecasting module		SW	Joint Venture (FINT, VICOM)	DSO/TSO (EPESA)
4	Galileo-enabled PMU signal monitoring module	Galileo added-value services	SW/ HW	Joint Venture (IREC, EUS)	DSO/TSO (EPESA), PMU Manufacturer

Figure 3: RESPONDENT's Key Exploitable Results

The development and marketing of these new tools and processes will consist of firstly refining the exploitable results (suites and modules) regarding their exploitation vision, distinctive features, maturity levels, and steps needed to maximize exploitation, market uptake, and commercialization. Research and analysis of these tasks have already begun as of May 2023, with the provision of a product/service formulation of the exploitable results to follow in deliverable *D7.5 – Exploitation Roadmap 1* in M12 and continually as the project progresses. A marketing strategy, as well as individual and joint exploitation pathways, will also be created and followed. These results have commercial or social significance and can be exploited as stand-alone products, processes, services, etc.

The methodology of development and marketing of the tools will follow a user-driven approach, as there is a high percentage of end users as beneficiaries in the consortium. Efforts will be made to ensure that the project outcomes comply with end user needs and have strong commercial potential. Moreover, a specific focus will be placed upon reaching, engaging, and synergising with key stakeholders to maximise project outcomes and the exploitation of the project's KERs.

For this reason, the exploitation strategy will be coordinated with the dissemination and communication strategy, using several tools to raise awareness and interest among key stakeholders (e.g., project branding, online presence), to demonstrate and promote acceptance of the KERs (scientific publications, pilots, and validation activities), and to promote the uptake and adoption of project KERs (exploitation strategies).

The objective of deliverable *D7.5 - Exploitation Roadmap 1* will, therefore, be to identify and initiate the management of the Exploitable Results (ERs) of the project, as well as to create the framework for their post-project market uptake and exploitation. The expected outcome of these efforts is a list of exploitable results and a methodology for a structured and synchronised approach to deal with them during the project that will be expanded upon in the first Exploitation Roadmap. In this way, all available opportunities are identified, actions are planned and executed, and the project partners can start to develop business plans for their exploitable results.

2.4 Target Audiences

The main target audiences for RESPONDENT were identified in the early stages of the project with input from all partners, and facilitated a strategic approach to targeted dissemination efforts from the beginning. However, it is important to recognise that the identification of target audiences is a fluid exercise, one that evolves and adapts as partners continually seek to engage with new individuals and entities of interest through their work.

For the sake of terminological clarification, audiences are defined as the receivers of messages and communications that the project partners are seeking to engage. Stakeholders, on the other hand, can be defined as groups or individuals who are directly impacted by the outcomes of the project, or have a vested interest in the results.

Once target audiences are engaged and begin to show an interest in the project, the idea is that they will then become stakeholders. In this deliverable, however, the terms ‘target audiences’ and ‘stakeholders’ will be used interchangeably.

Target audiences are identified based on the fact that they:

- have an interest in the project research and a desire to learn the outcomes.
- can contribute to the project achieving its objectives and have an influence elsewhere.
- may be directly or indirectly affected by the research.

Based on these criteria, the target audiences for RESPONDENT have been broken down into six main groups and are presented in Figure 3 below.

 RESPONDENT

Figure 4: RESPONDENT Target Audiences

2.5 Key Messages

It is important that key messages are tailored to each target audience, and to recognise that they may vary depending on the context in which they are used. Messages, therefore, are not fixed, but can and should change with time and circumstances.

When it comes to messaging, there is no ‘one size fits all’ approach to creating the appropriate communication method or style. This means that messages and other dissemination activities must be crafted on an individual basis. Collective brainstorming among the project partners will regularly take place to ensure that additional key messages are established and can be used in stakeholder engagement activities.

The initial tagline of RESPONDENT, which also serves as a key message, is “Increasing the viability of renewable energy sources in Europe’s energy sector”. It effectively summaries the essence of what RESPONDENT aims to achieve in eleven words.

A set of preliminary and broad key messages is presented below in Figure 4.

Figure 5: RESPONDENT Key Messages

2.6 Digital Communication and Dissemination Channels

To maximise the chances of achieving far-reaching impact with our dissemination activities, a combination of both traditional and digital channels will be employed, as well as to balance the effective aspects of both. High impact materials, in line with project branding, are used across all channels. For brand guidelines and further details on the branding, please see *Deliverable 7.1 – RESPONDENT Website*.

As a valuable tool of communication in the modern world, social media provides RESPONDENT with extensive opportunities to inform target audiences and promote adoption of the project’s results. Utilisation of social media will also assist in building and strengthening relationships with these target audiences, and will enable

individuals and entities to share their insights, experiences, and opinions as the project progresses. Ultimately, social media facilitates the coalescence of communities of people and businesses with common interests, both nationally and internationally.

For RESPONDENT, a social media grid will be created that will plot the social media channels considered most appropriate for reaching specific groups among the selected target audiences. In addition, a content maintenance plan will be drafted to effectively manage the streaming of information across our social media channels to secure and maintain followers.

Social and digital media will be especially useful in helping to create ‘communities of support’ for the project. By employing visual media, videos, icons, info-graphic imagery, and mobile enabled content, the project will generate interest through rich content experiences for any and all users of RESPONDENT’s digital platforms.

At Month 6 of the project, RESPONDENT already has a robust online identity due to its website and active presence on Twitter and LinkedIn. A RESPONDENT YouTube channel has also been created, which will feature engaging videos, interviews, and other content as the project advances and content is recorded/gathered.

Although the creation of a Facebook page was identified as a target in the GA, the declining usership of and mass disengagement with Facebook as a social media platform has made it an unviable source of effective communication and dissemination. It was therefore agreed among the project partners that Facebook would not be used as part of the communication and dissemination efforts of RESPONDENT.

Regular attention and observation are also given to the viability of Twitter in terms of promoting the work of the project since Elon Musk’s takeover of the platform in October 2022. Its relevance as an effective platform for the purpose of engaging with target audiences of RESPONDENT will therefore be continually monitored and considered over the next few months.

2.6.1 Website

As stated in the GA and *Deliverable D7.1*, the RESPONDENT website (<https://respondent-project.eu/>) serves as the nucleus for project dissemination and communication, as well as a repository for project information, research outputs, and deliverables. Other digital channels will thus serve to amplify and expand upon the key messages that emanate from the project website.

The website is considered to be a powerful tool of dissemination, and is a key factor in terms of engaging with the target audiences of the project. The site is representative of the project’s branding, and contains well-presented, non-confidential project information.

The RESPONDENT website will be systematically refined and updated throughout the lifecycle of the project as progress is made, tasks are completed, and deliverables are published. News, events, and timely updates will be shared on the website as they become available, with input sought from all project partners in providing news on the progress of various work packages.

New sections that are due to be added to the website include Deliverables, Related Projects, and Downloads (where resources such as the Brand Guidelines will be available). Further sections can be added with ease as

and when identified by the partners. Details about the different components of the RESPONDENT solution suite will also be added as the results are generated.

In addition to serving as the nucleus for all project communication and dissemination activities, the website will also act as a virtual hub for all post-project activities and will stay live until the year 2030.

A website privacy policy outlines how the website collects and uses personal data, and can be viewed in Annex 1 of this document.

A screenshot of the RESPONDENT website landing page is presented below in Figure 5.

Figure 6: RESPONDENT Website Landing Page

2.6.2 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn 'company' page was set up at the outset of the project:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/respondent-project-eu/?viewAsMember=true>

RESPONDENT's LinkedIn is predominantly used to raise awareness of the project and to engage with relevant/potential stakeholders. Interested individuals and organisations are encouraged to follow the LinkedIn page to keep up to date with the project's latest developments. The LinkedIn icon is displayed along the bottom right of the project website, and can be easily found by anyone wishing to keep abreast of the project and its outputs.

Project news and related news articles will also be cross posted across all RESPONDENT platforms. Partners are thus encouraged to share posts, as well as to provide suggestions for content within their area of expertise to attract appropriate academic, policy, and industry stakeholders.

Figure 7: RESPONDENT LinkedIn Page

2.6.3 Twitter

The RESPONDENT Twitter account (https://twitter.com/RESPONDENT_EU) was also created from the outset of the project.

As with the LinkedIn page, the Twitter page primarily operates to promote awareness of the project and its progress among key stakeholders, to interact and build relationships with them, to disseminate project news and results, as well as to share interesting news and insights in fields related to the work of RESPONDENT.

Figure 8: RESPONDENT Twitter Page

2.6.4 YouTube

A RESPONDENT YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/@RESPONDENT_EU) was created in Month 6.

Project videos will be uploaded as they become available. Planned ideas for future video content include infographic explainer videos and spotlight interviews with project partners.

All RESPONDENT videos will be uploaded to and stored on the YouTube channel, and will be shared across the digital channels, embedded into tweets, and LinkedIn posts.

Figure 9: RESPONDENT YouTube Page

2.6.6 Newsletter

The RESPONDENT newsletter will provide regular updates on progress, results, and past and upcoming events. The newsletter will be produced using LinkedIn’s newsletter feature, and will be sent to its subscribers by email.

LinkedIn Newsletters are GDPR compliant, as first-tier connections are shown the newsletter and invited to subscribe, thus ensuring that the subscriber list is fully opted in. LinkedIn Newsletters is a relatively new feature on the platform but has a strong impact and direct link to attaining subscribers.

It is a straightforward process for readers to subscribe to the newsletter. As they can subscribe via the LinkedIn platform, the process does require the user to have a LinkedIn account. However, it does not require visiting a different third-party website to sign-up, making it homogenous with their everyday social media use. Whenever a LinkedIn Newsletter is published, an automatic notification is sent to subscribers and their inboxes, which will in turn increase awareness of the RESPONDENT project and its progress. Metrics can then be monitored in terms of the numbers of views that the newsletters are receiving.

The first RESPONDENT newsletter is scheduled to be published in summer 2023. At least two issues of the newsletter will be distributed each year.

2.7 Promotional Material

A range of promotional material will be produced and developed as part of the project. All dissemination material is to be produced in line with the RESPONDENT brand as outlined in *D7.1 – RESPONDENT Website*.

Promotional material to be designed includes project leaflets, posters, banners, and infographics that are updated annually. As noted in the GA, however, most of the content for RESPONDENT's promotional material will be produced in digital form to minimise the environmental impact of the project.

Dissemination materials can be made available in editable form to the project team for the purpose of localisation for each pilot area. Partners will therefore be able to edit text fields and translate the text into their own languages where relevant.

A standardised PowerPoint template has already been designed and implemented for both internal and external presentations.

A QR (quick response) code will be made for use in selected materials where applicable.

Additional resources will be developed as identified and required by the project consortium.

2.8 Publications

The RESPONDENT project will cover a spectrum of disciplines. As a result, we expect outcomes in a range of scientific fields, including multi-disciplinary and interdisciplinary areas.

The RESPONDENT project is determined to make major efforts towards publishing in peer-reviewed, leading international journals, as well as in conference presentations. RESPONDENT is strongly committed to promoting open science research, and all the scientific articles and conference papers produced will be published according to the Horizon Europe Open Access guidelines and made publicly available. Special arrangements will be made to guarantee the security and confidentiality of restricted information.

It is important to coordinate information about scientific publications in progress to avoid potential risks and conflicts, such as simultaneous or repeated submissions, or potential objections to the publication from project partners. To guarantee that publications can proceed as planned, the lead partner of the publication should follow the steps outlined below:

- As early as possible and at least 30 days in advance, the lead partner informs the Project Coordinator (FINT) and the Dissemination Manager (CARR) about a planned scientific publication.
- Provide the following provisional details of the planned publication:
 - o Author(s), partner organisation(s);
 - o Title of the publication;
 - o Links to relevant project task(s);
 - o Research data to be used;
 - o Target journal(s);
 - o Planned submission date;
 - o Open access arrangement.

All publications will be recorded in the RESPONDENT Dissemination and Communication Tracker maintained by CARR, with the support of all partners. The dissemination tracker will keep record of the project scientific publications and act as a valuable database. An overview of the purpose of the Dissemination and Communication Tracker and its instructions for use can be viewed in the below figure:

Dissemination & Communication Tracker	Instructions for Use
Dissemination KPIs Target Events Events attended Journals & Publications Media Coverage Articles Generated by Partners Social Media Coverage Theses	<p><i>This dissemination and communication activities tracker is managed by WP7 leaders (CARR). The purpose of this spreadsheet is to track the project's KPI progress within WP7 and identify and share communication and dissemination opportunities related to the tExtended project such as events, target networks and target journals and publications. There are eight separate sections in the tracker - linked in the column to the left. Many of these headings are linked to a KPI outlined in the project Grant Agreement, you can see an overview of all WP7 communications and dissemination KPIs in section three. The material in this spreadsheet will also facilitate planning for project news items, e.g. website articles, and social media posts.</i></p> <p><i>WP7 leaders (CARR) will manage updating the worksheet, however, all partners are welcomed and encouraged to input suggested events, networks and journals and publications. For example, you can input an event which you and/or your team are attending or you can share the event for the interest of the consortium i.e. if the event may be suitable for a different partner. Don't hesitate to contact CARR if you have any questions. Thank you for your assistance.</i></p>

Figure 10: Dissemination and Communication Tracker

It is essential that each partner assesses and chooses the most suitable publication based on the following criteria: field, ranking, scientific impact, prestige, readership, and open access policy.

An initial selection of publications, as identified by all members of the Consortium to be targeted, is presented below in Table 3.

Table 3: Selection of Targeted Journals

Journal title	Publisher	Homepage
Citizen Science: Theory and Practice	Ubiquity Press	https://theoryandpractice.citizenscienceassociation.org/
Energies	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	https://www.mdpi.com/
European Journal of Electrical Engineering & Computer Science (EJECE)	European Open Science	https://www.ejece.org/index.php/ejece
European Journal of Energy Research	European Open Science	https://www.ej-energy.org/index.php/eienergy

IEEE Transactions on Power Systems	IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=59
IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid	IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=5165411
IET Smart Grid	Wiley	https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/hub/journal/25152947/homepage/productinformation.html
International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-applied-earth-observation-and-geoinformation
International Journal of Energy Research	Wiley	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1099114x
International Journal of Environmental Monitoring and Analysis (IJEMA)	Science Publishing Group	https://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/j/ijema
Renewable Energy	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-energy
Smart Energy	IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/smart-energy?_gl=1*_9shvwf*_ga*Mzk5MDA2OTI1LjE2Nzk0ODkxODQ.*_ga_4R527DM8F7*MTY3OTQ4OTE4NC4xLjAuMTY3OTQ4OTE4NC4wLjAuMA..
Sustainability	MDPI	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability
Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks (SEGAN)	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/sustainable-energy-grids-and-networks
The International Journal of	Elsevier Ltd.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-electrical-power-and-energy-systems

Electrical Power & Energy Systems (JEPE)		
--	--	--

2.9 Events

It is planned that RESPONDENT will be represented and promoted at a wide range of events throughout the lifetime of the project. These include virtual and physical, scientific and industry conferences and exhibitions, workshops, trade shows, and seminars/webinars relevant either to the areas of expertise of the partners or to the project as a whole.

Due to their specific areas of expertise and work, all partner organisations will play key roles in presenting the project, its progress, and results at a diverse range of events. Details of event participation will be shared on the project website, social channels, and in newsletters, as well as in periodic progress reports to the EC.

The below table includes target events that were identified by partners at the outset of the project. These events are seen as relevant to RESPONDENT through the work of one or more partner organisations.

Many of the events listed are annual or biennial. If it is the case that this year's event turns out to be soon for RESPONDENT, the event in question can be targeted in the proceeding year instead. This list is regularly updated as part of the RESPONDENT dissemination and communications tracker.

Table 4: Selection of Targeted Events

Start Date	End Date	Event Name	Event Type	Location	Website
17/03/2023	17/03/2023	Copernicus Thematic Workshop: Energy	Workshop	Brussels, Belgium	https://euspa.blum.m.it/event/ar/3/euspa-copernicus-online-event
20/04/2023	20/04/2023	En-ROADS Climate Workshop	Workshop/ Webinar	Washington, D.C., USA	https://www.climateinteractive.org/get-involved/webinars/
22/04/2023	23/04/2023	International Conference on Electrical and Electronics Engineering	Conference	NITTTR, Chandigarh, India	https://iceee.in/
25/04/2023	28/04/2023	EU Knowledge	Forum	Online	https://research-innovation-community.ec.europa.eu/events/rF2UaV

		Valorisation Week			BFdp7axYkmpZ0Q4/overview
03/05/2023	03/05/2023	Renpower Greece	Conference	Athens, Greece	https://euroconventionglobal.com/event/renpower-greece-2023/
03/06/2023	11/06/2023	EU Green Week 2023 Conference	Conference	Brussels, Belgium	https://green-week.event.europa.eu/index_en
07/06/2023	08/06/2023	Clean Energy for EU Islands	Forum	Saaremaa, Estonia	https://clean-energy-islands.ec.europa.eu/register-now-clean-energy-eu-islands-forum-2023
12/06/2023	15/06/2023	CIREDD International Conference on Electricity Distribution	Forum	Rome, Italy	https://www.cired2023.org/
14/06/2023	16/06/2023	Intersolar Europe	Exhibition	Munich, Germany	https://www.intersolar.de/home
16/07/2023	20/07/2023	IEEE PES General Meeting	Conference	Orlando, Florida, USA	https://pes-gm.org/
09/09/2023	10/09/2023	Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF)	Exhibition	Thessaloniki, Greece	https://www.thessalonikifair.gr/en
07/11/2023	09/11/2023	Smart City Expo World Congress	Exhibition	Barcelona, Spain	https://www.smartcityexpo.com/the-event/
28/11/2023	30/11/2023	Enlit Europe	Forum	Paris, France	https://www.enlit-europe.com/welcome

03/12/2023	06/12/2023	2023 International Conference on Energy Technologies for Future Grids	Conference	Wollongong, NSW, Australia	https://attend.ieee.org/etfg-2023/
06/02/2024	08/02/2024	Genera	Fair	Madrid, Spain	https://www.ifema.es/genera

2.10 Clustering, networking, and knowledge transfer activities

Clustering and networking can be useful for dissemination and exploitation activities. There is potential for RESPONDENT to build upon close collaboration with other research and innovation projects and relevant stakeholders in the areas of climate change, renewable energy sources, machine learning, AI algorithms, and power grid infrastructure, to name but a few.

Pre-existing networks and research collaborations, especially where project partners are already involved, can be used to achieve a broader impact, and ensure a wider adoption of the developed technologies and other state-of-the-art research outputs by end-users.

2.10.1 Clustering with related projects

Clustering and the creation of synergies with relevant projects has several advantages. Cluster projects can actively promote each other, and they can share knowledge and results and align certain dissemination activities. RESPONDENT will explore the possibilities for both technical and dissemination clustering as the project continues to progress.

Technical clustering allows for cross-fertilisation of ideas and concepts, as well as the sharing of insights and best practices while avoiding duplication of efforts. Dissemination clustering facilitates the amplifying of the projects' stories and messages by one another and leads to increased visibility through collaboration (joint newsletters, joint press releases, cross promotion on social media, etc.).

Collaboration opportunities with similar HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE-02-51 projects and other Horizon Europe projects will be sought to facilitate effective communication and ensure far-reaching impact. Joint information and dissemination activities will be undertaken to increase synergies between, and the visibility of EU research and innovation actions.

Common Dissemination Booster (CDB) services promoted by the EC will also be considered.

A draft list of related projects is presented in Annex A3: Related Projects.

2.10.2 Building networks

RESPONDENT will benefit from a network of pre-existing communications, associations, and initiatives to ensure active engagement with and involvement of a diverse range of stakeholders in its own activities. The

consortium partners already have a pre-existing network of contacts, clients, and business partners across Europe, which can all be utilised to reach and engage with different stakeholders.

All partners are committed to contributing to networking through a variety of activities that includes attendance at events, issuing newsletters, and organising focus groups and workshops.

2.10.3 Knowledge transfer activities

Knowledge transfer activities that will be explored with partners as part of the project's dissemination and communication efforts include a white paper, workshops, conference presentations, open-access peer reviewed publications, and the pilot events.

RESPONDENT will also leverage the knowledge and expertise of the related stakeholders and end-users, such as the RES aggregators, TSOs/DSOs, and power grid operators.

2.11 Media and multipliers

The media is a crucial audience for the work of RESPONDENT, as well as being an effective multiplier channel to reach other priority audience groups.

In terms of media relations, the focus in the first year of the project from a dissemination and communications perspective will be to grow the media contact database (inclusive of media outlets at the local, national, and EU level), to issue press releases, and to gain media coverage of RESPONDENT's preliminary results with the public once they have been generated.

Further proposed activities include 1-on-1 media briefings with key journalists, pitching potential interview opportunities with project partners, drafting articles to pitch to industry publications, and the provision of media training to key spokespeople within the project consortium. Local media in particular will be targeted in the pilot areas of Greece and Spain as a joint effort between CARR and the pilot partners. News/press releases will be translated into local languages where relevant.

Efforts involved with respect to media relations will continue throughout the duration of the project. As the results of the RESPONDENT solution suite begin to take shape, media activities will become increasingly results focused.

The RESPONDENT progress, results, and overall story will also be presented to EU-level media outlets with a view to obtain coverage in e.g. the Euronews Futuris series (<https://www.euronews.com/next/next-series/futuris>).

In addition to this series, there exists a wealth of valuable EC resources that can serve as amplifiers and multipliers of the RESPONDENT messages. The EC offers to support the dissemination efforts of projects that it funds, and RESPONDENT will be grateful for any visibility given to the project through EC media outlets over the course of its lifespan. Such outlets include:

- Horizon Magazine: <https://horizon-magazine.eu/>
- Project Stories: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551/>

- research*eu results magazine ('Project of the Month' feature or other): <https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu>
- Research*eu focus: <https://op.europa.eu/en/home>
- European Research Executive Agency networks: https://twitter.com/REA_research

2.12 Timeline of Activities

An indicative timeline of communication and dissemination activities from M7-M18 of the project is presented in the below table.

Table 5: Indicative Timeline of Activities

Activity	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
Task 7.1: Communication and Dissemination Activities, including Stakeholder Engagement									
WP7 calls									
Website updates									
Twitter updates									
LinkedIn updates									
YouTube updates									
Newsletters									
Promotional material (leaflet, poster, pull-up design)									
Event attendance/hosting									
Annual review of website									
Media contacts database created									
Media briefings, media training									
Press release issued to media									
D7.3 Dissemination and Communication Report 1									
T7.2: Exploitation Roadmap									
Development and marketing of new tools and processes									
Creation and provision of services									

Further research activities									
T7.3 Business Planning, and Market & Commercialisation Strategies and Innovation Management									
Determination of initial business models for the RESPONDENT solution suite									

2.13 Performance Measurement and Analysis

In terms of the communication and dissemination activities, measuring and monitoring their success can be a difficult task with numerous variables to consider. Not all success factors are tangible, nor can all elements leading to impactful dissemination be possible to quantify.

Despite these challenges, it is possible to identify certain numerical targets that can facilitate the measuring of how well the project is achieving its dissemination goals. These are included in the key performance indicators (KPIs) as outlined in the GA, and will be monitored by CARR regularly.

2.13.1 Key Performance Indicators

The metrics that are presented in the below table represent the quantifiable targets against key communication and dissemination activities for the duration of the project.

Per section 2.2.4. of the GA, these metrics represent the communication KPIs of the RESPONDENT project. Figures are cumulative and reflect the outlook at the start of the project. The numeric values will be reviewed as the project progresses, with *D7.3* providing the first update on the status and potential readjustments (up or down) at M15.

Table 6: Key Performance Indicators

No.	Activity	Indicator	Goal by M30	Source
1	Project website	Visits	8,000	Google Analytics
	Deliverables, reports, communication collateral etc.	Downloads	100	
	Blog posts and news updates on the website	Views	Monthly	
2	Newsletter	Publications	6	LinkedIn reports
3	Social Media Platforms	Followers	1000 (LinkedIn and Twitter combined)	LinkedIn reports, Twitter analytics
4	Videos	Published videos	6	YouTube Analytics
5	Articles/publications in media	Number	20	Project records
	Press releases	Number	6	
	Open-access scientific publications	Number	2	
6	Conference presentations	Number	2	Project records

7	Trade Fair	Number	1	Project records
8	Workshops	Number	2	Project records
9	White Papers produced	Number	1	Project records
10	Public Webinar	Number	1	Project records

2.13.2 Online Analytics

In terms of measuring the impact of the project’s online dissemination and communication activities, we will rely on several available tools, such as Google Analytics and YouTube Analytics.

Google Analytics is a free web analytics tool that enables us to understand and analyse the overall performance and trends of the RESPONDENT website. It is used to measure website traffic patterns, such as the total number of visitors, page views, duration of visits, downloads, and the geographical location of visitors. This information is useful in terms of gaining insights into the performance of the website, which will in turn provide feedback on how we can improve and optimise the website’s structure and thus match the website with the preference of visitors.

In RESPONDENT, Google Analytics will be used to track the number of visits and to analyse trends in the behaviours of visitors to the project’s website. Continuous monitoring of such data will be carried out throughout the project. By observing these analytics, useful insights may be obtained, including how long visitors remain on the website, how many pages of the website visitors view, where they are spending most of their time, and which content was most popular. The content and structure of the website may then be tailored to satisfy the interests of the website visitors, thus attracting additional traffic. As search engine optimisation is a key element in promoting traffic to a website, the website therefore needs to be updated regularly with content which includes key tag words, which will in turn allow Google to prioritise websites based on the search words selected by users.

The website will thus undergo an annual review across the lifespan of the project, utilising the obtained analytics and feedback from partners to improve the website’s performance. If it is determined that a particular section of the website is more frequently visited than others, we will be able to feature it more prominently on the site and ensure that the navigation journey to that section is easier for visitors.

Google Analytics will also be used to analyse and monitor the performance of RESPONDENT’s social media channels, namely Twitter and LinkedIn. Analytical reports will help to measure the activity and optimise the performance of our Twitter and LinkedIn pages in terms of the number of posts, the best times to post, profile visits, new followers, and impressions.

Although the number of followers we receive on these channels represent our main performance indicators, we will also rely on the impression metrics and the number of shares/likes to improve our engagement rate and the overall performance of our social media posts. Potential improvements may include timing, tags, and the number of posts in our social media calendar.

In addition to Google Analytics, we will also employ the use of YouTube Analytics to monitor the performance of the RESPONDENT YouTube channel and posted project videos. Such performance indicators for our

YouTube channel include the number of views, demographics, and specifications of devices used for viewing our visual content.

2.14 Management and Administration of Dissemination Activities

CARR is the WP7 Leader and the Communication and Dissemination Manager of the project. This means that CARR is responsible for the successful planning, creating, and developing of the communication and dissemination strategy and activities. This will take place in close cooperation with all consortium partners.

As the two RESPONDENT pilot demonstrations will take place in Greece and Spain, the partners that are based in these countries will play a key role in the dissemination activities in the run-up to and during the pilot campaigns.

All partners are informed about the management of the dissemination activities through the monthly calls and emails. The coordinator and specific partners are consulted on relevant issues when necessary.

The dissemination tracker will be maintained by CARR as a continuously updated database of all RESPONDENT dissemination and communication activities. The tracker includes seven sections and are listed below:

1. Future Events
2. Events Attended
3. Published Publications
4. Relevant Journals/Publications
5. Media Coverage
6. Articles Generated
7. List of Key Stakeholders

The dissemination and communications tracker may be updated throughout the lifetime of the project with new sections if new opportunities to disseminate the project's activities, work, and research arise.

2.14.1 Dissemination Reporting, Compliance, and Obligation to Disseminate Results

CARR maintains a record of all dissemination activities undertaken throughout the lifetime of the project. All partners will report any dissemination actions to CARR, either orally, during the monthly WP7 calls, or by email. Reported dissemination details feed into dissemination activities across all project platforms.

Informed consent is always obtained from individuals taking part in dissemination activities, such as interviews, photos, and videos. Copyright and GDPR compliance are also always ensured. For details on consent forms and data management, see deliverable *D1.2 – Data Management Plan*.

As stated in article 16 of the GA, beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving a notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In

such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

2.14.2 Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data

RESPONDENT's open access approach ensures that the results of the partners' research contributes invaluable knowledge into the marketplace of climate change solutions. Our ability to reconcile an open access approach for data and results generated with the business interests of the participating industry has the potential to offer a successful case study in terms of knowledge management for future projects developing technologies for solutions to climate change, as well as the energy crisis and energy security in Europe.

As stated in RESPONDENT's GA, beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, it must be ensured that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository, such as Zenodo, for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must also retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine actionable) and provide information, at a minimum, about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

With regards to research data management, information on how this will be used during the RESPONDENT project is outlined in *D1.2 – Data Management Plan*.

2.14.3 Acknowledgement of EU Funding

RESPONDENT uses the European flag (emblem) in all communication and dissemination materials to acknowledge the support received under the Horizon Europe programme.

The European Union emblem must not be modified or merged with any other graphic element or text. If other logos are displayed in addition to the EU emblem, the latter must be at least the same size as the biggest of the other logos. The typeface used in conjunction with the EU emblem must stay simple and easily readable. The recommended typefaces are Arial, Auto, Calibri, Garamond, Tahoma, Trebuchet, Ubuntu, and Verdana. The colour of the font should be Reflex Blue (the same colour as the European flag), white, or black, depending

on the background. The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem. More details on the rules are available in the operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding: The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027 (European Commission 2021).

The emblem is associated with the following sentence: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101082355.” Where relevant, the following sentence is added: “The material presented and views expressed here are the responsibility of the author(s) only. The EU Commission takes no responsibility for any use made of the information set out.”

2.14.4 Risk Management

Measures for risk mitigation are in place (See Deliverable *D1.1 - Project Management and Risk Management Plan*).

A risk identified as relevant to the communication and dissemination strategy, as per the GA, is described as follows: “Failed or insufficient exploitation results by project partners” (Risk 8). The risk-mitigation measures involve the defining of clear, individual exploitation plans, the identification of future exploitable solutions, and a clear, coordinated business plan to be proposed. Further measures include ensuring awareness raising and engagement with the project through a broad palette of dissemination activities tailored to key stakeholder groups.

Queries from the stakeholders will be responded to without delay. CARR will oversee the filtering out of irrelevant and inappropriate content and comments posted on any of RESPONDENT’s social media accounts. If negative feedback is received on the project’s social channels, it will be acknowledged, taken offline, resolved, and finally addressed online. If the nature of the feedback is abusive, blocking and reporting the user in question will be considered. However, as the project’s resources are limited, there is a heavy reliance on all partners to flag any content they spot that needs to be attended to. This includes cases where the local language of one of the partners is in question.

There is also a need to be prepared for the unexpected. A sudden, unexpected event related to the project’s team or a publication in a high-ranking journal may call for an instant reaction from the RESPONDENT consortium. Here, again, all partners are reminded of the need to keep up to date, follow turns of events, and notify the relevant members of the consortium in such instances.

As stated in the GA (Art. 17), before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority. Such communication activity could include major media coverage (online or printed press, broadcast media, social media, etc.) that will go beyond having a local impact and which could have the potential for national and/or international outreach. The RESPONDENT partners are fully aware of and compliant with this requirement.

3 Conclusions

This deliverable has provided a detailed picture of the communication and dissemination plan for RESPONDENT.

This deliverable will serve, first and foremost, a guideline for the consortium partners for their dissemination and communication activities. The document will therefore serve as an invaluable blueprint and reference in terms of proceeding with the dissemination and communication activities of the project, both for CARR as the leader of *Work Package 7 – Roadmap to Impact* and for the consortium as a whole.

It has presented the communication and dissemination plan of the project, including clearly defined objectives and the identification of key target audiences, messages, and channels. It has listed promotional material to be used in dissemination activities. It has selected relevant scientific and industry publications as well as conferences and other events to target over the coming years. It has presented an indicative timeline of the described dissemination activities and explained how their performance is measured and analysed, and finally provided an overview of the management aspects.

This report marks the first full draft of the RESPONDENT plan for communication and dissemination. Its contents will feed into *D7.3 – Dissemination and Communication Report 1* in Month 15, and *D7.4 – Dissemination and Communication Report 2* in Month 30.

The initial plan for communication and dissemination serves as a solid foundation for ensuring that generated project results are disseminated effectively and systematically.

References

- [1] European Commission (2022) Horizon Europe (HORIZON) – Programme Guide, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
- [2] European Commission (2021). Use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027. Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding. Retrieved on 14 April 2023 from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf
- [3] European Commission (2021). Use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027. Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding. Retrieved on 14 April 2023 from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf
- [4] European Commission (2021). Use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027. Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding. Retrieved on 12 April 2023 from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

Annexes

A1: Website Privacy Policy

Introduction

Thank you for visiting the RESPONDENT website. This website is dedicated to the dissemination of the RESPONDENT project, funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101082355.

This privacy policy is part of the RESPONDENT website and **solely concerns the processing of personal data that occurs in connection with the operation of this website**. This privacy policy explains how Carr Communications ("We", "Us"), the administrator of the RESPONDENT website, uses personal data collected from when you use the website and when you provide your details to us via the contact form available on the website (<https://respondent-project.eu/contact/>).

In particular, this privacy policy will help you to find information on:

- who is legally responsible for the data processing (data controller)
- the data collection and logging that we carry out automatically when you visit our website
- the data that we collect and process when you contact us via the contact form or when you sign up for our newsletter
- Your rights as a data subject
- Your right to lodge a complaint

Who We Are

RESPONDENT is a research and innovation project, which seeks to bolster and support the integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into Europe's power grid infrastructure. The core objectives of RESPONDENT are to develop and promote the integration of RES into Europe's existing power grids, as well as to demonstrate their viability and reliability compared to traditional sources of energy that are wreaking havoc on global temperatures and accelerating the most destructive impacts of our rapidly changing climate.

The RESPONDENT Consortium consists of 8 partner organisations representing 3 countries across Europe – Ireland, Spain, and Greece. The project has been funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No. 101082355. It is coordinated by Future Intelligence Ltd. (FINT). Carr Communications is the RESPONDENT partner responsible for the dissemination and communication efforts of the project.

Carr Communications is committed to processing personal data responsibly, securely, and proportionally throughout our activities in compliance with the EU [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\) 2016/679](#).

For the purposes of this website, the responsible data controller is **Carr Communications**, registered in Dublin, Ireland, under registered number 42175, with a registered office at 24 Fitzwilliam Place, Dublin 2, D02 T296, Ireland.

You can contact us:

- by e-mail at info@carrcommunications.ie
- by telephone: (+353.1) 772 8900
- by fax: (+353.1) 772 8901

Please explicitly mention “RESPONDENT” in the subject line of your communication.

What Data We Collect

Automatically collected usage data

When you access the RESPONDENT website on your device, we may automatically collect certain usage data, which may include:

- Date and time of access
- Duration of visit
- Your operating system
- The device you have used for access
- Browser type (including version)
- Referrer (name of the website that you accessed immediately before)
- Volume of data sent
- IP address
- Unique device identifiers and other diagnostic data.

Data provided by you

By contacting us through the website contact form, you will provide us with (and we will collect) your contact details, such as:

- your **name**
- your **email** address, and
- the **message** you submitted.

We are **not collect** any metadata that you did not expressly provide us with.

Purpose of Data Collection

We process your personal data for the following purposes:

- to provide this page to you (usage data)
- to use your personal data for ensuring the security of the page
- to respond to your messages/queries
- to provide you with our newsletter when you subscribe to it.

Legal Bases of Processing

Legitimate interest

For the **data that we collect automatically**, we rely on Article 6 (1) point f of the GDPR (i.e. *legitimate interest*), as they are required for us to provide the service, to ensure technical operation and to investigate and remove

any malfunctions of the website and to ensure the page's security. It is in our interest to ensure the use and technical operability of our website. This data is automatically processed when our website is accessed. Unless they are provided, you cannot use our service.

Consent

For the **personal data that you provide us with through the contact form**, we rely on your **consent** (Article 6(1)a of the GDPR), which you express by completing and submitting the contact form, or by actively signing up to our newsletter.

How We Protect Your Data

We have put technical and organisational security measures and procedures in place to protect your personal data from loss, misuse, alteration, or destruction. We have made efforts to collect the minimum information needed to respond to your messages/requests.

We install and regularly update all security and anti-virus software in use on all our systems.

Although we have rigorous technical and organisational security procedures in place to keep your personal data secure, including the use of an SSL certificate, you are advised to remember that the Internet is not always a secure medium and that transmissions over the Internet are never completely private or secure.

If you are unsure about submitting any personal data to us, please contact us instead via telephone, fax or post.

How Long We Keep Your Data

We retain personal data only as long as it is necessary for the purposes described above i.e. to respond to your request or message. We erase this data **after 6 months** of the last communication unless there is a legal duty to keep the data for longer periods, such as due to accounting regulations or keeping evidence of legal requests. If the data is no longer required for the relevant purpose, we erase the data **within 24 hours**.

Do We Share Personal Data with Third Parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties, such as those listed below, to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we will ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before sharing the data with them.

We may engage with several or all of the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., the host of this website)
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers and auditors
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies (e.g., tax authorities) or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with, applicable law or regulation

Do We Transfer Your Personal Data Outside of the EU?

By default, we store personal data on servers located in the EU.

What Are Your Data Protection Rights?

As a data subject, you can exercise the rights outlined in this section of the privacy policy. We may need to request specific information from you to help us confirm your identity and ensure your right to access the information or to exercise any of your other rights. This helps us ensure that personal data is not disclosed to any person who has no right to receive it. No fee is required to make an initial request unless your request is clearly unfounded or excessive. Depending on the circumstances, we may be unable to comply with your request based on other lawful grounds.

Right to access (GDPR Art. 15)

You have the right to obtain confirmation as to whether processing of your personal data takes place in connection with the operation of the RESPONDENT website. If this is the case, you can request access to the data that we store about you. Granting the right to access will only occur where your identification is possible.

Right to rectification (Art. 16)

You have the right to obtain the rectification of inaccurate personal data concerning you. The exercise of this right is only possible where you can be identified and the inaccuracy of data is verified.

Restriction of processing (Art. 18)

You have the right to obtain the restriction of processing, where:

- the accuracy of your personal data is contested;
- the processing is lawful, but you oppose the erasure of personal data and request the restriction of processing instead;
- we as the controller no longer need your personal data, but you require the data to establish, exercise or defend legal claims;
- you have objected to processing pursuant to GDPR Article 21.1 pending the verification of whether the legitimate grounds of ours (as the controller) override those of yours.

The exercise of this right may require provision of further information to allow your identification as described in the right to access.

Right to object (Art. 21)

A legal basis for the processing of your personal data in connection with the operation of the RESPONDENT website is Art. 6.1(f) of the GDPR (our legitimate interest) or 6.1(a) (your consent). At any time, you shall have the right to object to the processing of your data, on grounds relating to your particular situation, unless we can demonstrate compelling legitimate grounds for the processing that override your interests, rights, and freedoms, or for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims.

The exercise of this right may require provision of further information to allow your identification.

Right to erasure ('Right to be forgotten') (Art. 17)

You have the right to obtain erasure of your personal data, if:

- you object to the processing pursuant to Art. 21.1 and there are no overriding legitimate grounds;
- your personal data has been unlawfully processed;
- your personal data must be erased for compliance with a legal obligation in Union or Member State law to which we as the controller are subject.

Right to data portability (Art. 20)

If you have provided us with data based on your consent, and as long as there are legal grounds, you can request that we send you the data you gave us in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format, or you can request for us to send your data to a different controller.

To exercise any of the aforementioned rights, please contact us at info@carrcommunications.ie. When you do so, please make sure that we can clearly identify you.

Right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority (Art. 77)

You have the right to lodge a complaint with a data protection supervisory authority in the Member State of your habitual residence, place of work, or place of the alleged infringement if you believe that the processing of your personal data infringes the GDPR.

A list of national supervisory authorities can be found [here](#) (this links to a third-party website – official website of the European Commission).

Disclaimer and Limitations of Liability

We aim to keep the information that appears on the RESPONDENT website as complete and up to date as possible. If errors are brought to our attention, we will take all reasonable steps to make any necessary corrections within a reasonable timeframe.

Please be aware that the information published on our website is for informational purposes only. None of the information contained on the website constitutes legal or professional advice, nor can we accept responsibility for how it might be used, and we are not responsible or liable for any errors or omissions in any of the information provided on the website. We cannot be held liable for any direct or indirect damage that may result from use of this site. Links to other websites are provided in good faith and for informational purposes only. A link to another website does not mean that we endorse or accept any responsibility for the content or use of such website.

While we take all possible steps to minimise disruption caused by technical errors, we cannot guarantee that our website will not be interrupted or otherwise affected by such problems. Please note that access may be suspended temporarily and without notice in the case of system failure, website maintenance, or repair for reasons beyond our control.

The use of our website is governed by the law of the Republic of Ireland. Any dispute arising from or related to the use of this website shall be subject to the non-exclusive jurisdiction of the Irish courts.

Do We Link to Other Websites?

Our websites may contain links to other sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, which are not governed by this privacy policy. Please review the destination websites' privacy policies before submitting personal data on those sites. Whilst we try to link only to sites that share our standards and respect for privacy, we are not responsible for the content, security, or privacy practices employed by other sites.

How We Use Social Media

We use social media to communicate information about the project through widely used channels, such as Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube. You can access RESPONDENT accounts on social media platforms directly from our website. In order to protect your privacy, our social media buttons or components to connect to those services do not set cookies when our web pages are loaded on your device.

Each social media channel has their own policy on the way they process your personal data when you access their sites. If you would like to watch one of the RESPONDENT videos on YouTube, you will be asked to accept YouTube cookies; if you look at our activity on Twitter, you will be asked to accept Twitter cookies; the same applies for LinkedIn.

If you have any concerns or questions about their use of your personal data, please carefully read their respective privacy policies before using them. The use of social media by RESPONDENT, including Twitter and LinkedIn, does not in any way imply an endorsement of Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, and their privacy policies.

The ideas and views expressed by RESPONDENT on social media are for information purposes only. Views and opinions expressed do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health or any other affiliated body. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Do We Review the Privacy Policy?

We regularly review our website's privacy policy and will post any updates to it on this webpage. This privacy policy was last updated on 5th April 2023.

Contact Us

If you have any concerns as to how your data is processed, you can contact us by e-mail at info@carrcommunications.ie or by post: 24 Fitzwilliam Place, Dublin 2, D02 T296, Ireland.

We will respond to your queries within 30 days from when we receive them.

A2: Cookie Policy

Core Policy

A cookie is a small text file that is downloaded onto ‘terminal equipment’ (e.g., a computer or a smartphone) when you access a website. It allows the website to make user’s experience more efficient by recognising your device and by storing some information about your preferences or past actions. Cookies allow websites to remember your preferences and play an important role in making the site work better for you. To some extent, cookies can be seen as providing a “memory” for the website, enabling it to recognise a user and respond appropriately.

In accordance with law, we can store cookies on your device only if they are strictly necessary for the operation of this website. For all other types of cookies, we need your permission. This means that cookies which are categorized as necessary are processed based on Art.6.1(f) of the GDPR, i.e. our legitimate interest.

All other cookies, that is those from the category’s preferences and marketing, can be processed only based on your consent i.e. Art. 6.1 (a) of the GDPR. Please note that you can at any time change or withdraw your consent via our Cookie Management Tool that is available on our website.

How Do We Use Cookies?

This website uses different types of cookies. Some cookies are placed by third party services that appear on our pages (i.e. “third-party” cookies).

We use the following cookies and similar technologies:

Necessary Cookies

These cookies enable core functionality such as security, verification of identity, and network management, as well as ensuring that they make the website work. You may disable these by changing your browser settings, but this may affect how the website functions since the website cannot function properly without those cookies.

Non-necessary cookies

- **Functional cookies**

Preference cookies collect data to remember choices users make to improve and give a more personalised experience. They enable a website to remember information that changes the way the website behaves or what it looks like, your preferred language, text size, or the region that you are in. The information these cookies collect may be anonymised and they cannot track your browsing activity on other websites.

- **Marketing Cookies**

These cookies are normally used to track advertising effectiveness to provide a more relevant service and deliver better advertisements to suit your interests. However, since RESPONDENT is a research project, we **DO NOT use** any marketing cookies.

- **Analytics Cookies**

These cookies help us understand how visitors interact with our website or to discover errors. We use these cookies for internal research and analysis of our performance. The cookies simply assess how you interact with our website as an anonymous user (**the data gathered does not identify you personally**).

Also, this data is **not shared with any third parties** or used for any other purpose. The anonymised statistics will be included in a report analysing communication efforts on the RESPONDENT project.

However, you are **free to refuse** these types of cookies via the cookie management tool that you will see on the first page you visit.

We need your consent for the use of analytics cookies.

How Do I Manage My Cookie Preferences?

Our cookie management tool will allow you to specify your preferences for those cookies that are placed on your device by this website, and which are not strictly necessary for the functioning of it.

Just adjust the available sliders to 'On' or 'Off', then click 'Save and close'. You may need to refresh your page for your settings to take effect.

Alternatively, most web browsers allow some control of most cookies through the browser settings. To find out more about cookies, including how to see what cookies have been set, visit www.aboutcookies.org or www.allaboutcookies.org.

Find out how to manage cookies on popular browsers:

- [Google Chrome](#)
- [Microsoft Edge](#)
- [Mozilla Firefox](#)
- [Microsoft Internet Explorer](#)
- [Opera](#)
- [Apple Safari](#)

To find information relating to other browsers, visit the browser developer's website.

We regularly review this cookie policy and will post any updates to it on this webpage. This privacy policy was last updated on 5th April 2023.

A3: Related Projects

Funding source/topic	Project	Website	Description	CORDIS Link
HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE-02-51 - EGNSS and Copernicus applications fostering the European Green deal.	100KTREES	https://www.100ktree.eu/	Provides a decision toolbox for cities to improve air quality, biodiversity, human wellbeing and reduce climate risks by planting more trees.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082551
GALILEO-1-2014 - EGNSS applications	DEMETRA	https://www.inrim.it/it	DEMETRA aims to demonstrate the feasibility of delivering early EGNSS timing services to end users by utilising an operational demonstrator and conducting tests with pilot applications. Based on the current practice of national metrological laboratories, DEMETRA will define and develop a prototype of a European time disseminator, based on EGNSS.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/640658
LC-SC3-ES-6-2019 - Research on advanced tools and technological development	Smart4RES	https://www.smart4res.eu/	The Smart4RES project aims to bring substantial performance improvements to the whole model and value chain in	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/864337

			renewable energy (RES) forecasting, with particular emphasis placed on optimizing synergies with storage and to support power system operation and participation in electricity markets.	
SC5-01-2016-2017 - Exploiting the added value of climate services	S2S4E	https://s2s4e.eu/	The S2S4E project will create an operational climate service that will enable renewable energy producers and providers, electricity network managers and policy makers to design better-informed strategies at sub-seasonal to seasonal timescales.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776787
HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE-02-51 - EGNSS and Copernicus applications fostering the European Green deal	SWIFTT	https://swiftt.eu/	SWIFTT will provide forest managers with affordable, simple, and effective remote sensing tools backed up by Copernicus satellite imagery and powerful machine learning models.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082732